

ESSENTIAL TRENDS IN ACADEMIC MOBILITY (SAUM STUDY CASE)

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ABSTRACT. Academic mobility is a pivotal characteristic of the Higher Educational Institutions of the Republic of Moldova, offered by Erasmus+ programme, which the Covid-19 epidemic has lastingly disrupted.

Credit academic mobility has a significant importance in expanding cooperation between the European Union and the Eastern Partnership countries in the field of higher education and research.

Through the study of the major trends in academic mobility Erasmus+ programme provides an analytical tool to support higher education institutions that are led to redirect their international strategy by focusing their efforts on this region, its staff and its students.

Key words: *academic mobility, projects, globalization, strategy of internationalization.*

Introduction

Academic mobility is a necessity in the perspective of globalization, promoting coherence at European level and enriching the scientific horizon. This contributes to the development of the capacity to cope with a new environment learning and understanding other cultures. In the context of multiple problems with facing Eastern Partnership countries: poverty, corruption, lack of transparency, etc., the process of mobility of academic staff and students contributes to increasing the quality of studies by improving modern methods of teaching and learning, curricula adapted to the European context, and the content of the subject matter. This determines the rallying of education from Eastern Partnership countries to European quality standards in education.

Although the mobility process has many advantages, we still find that, currently, there are no integrated analytical reports and statistics that would show the evolution of the mobility process, the difficulties regarding student participation and the barriers faced by staff during the academic mobility period.

Also, the national statistics are fragmentary and do not identify the categories that could not be involved in the mobility process, as well as the share of these categories, disaggregated by sex, years of study, specialties, etc.

Today, the academic mobility of staff and students in higher education is known to have a great influence on the socio-economic success of the entire academic institution. The contribution and benefits of each country are known and explained.

Materials and methods

The reflected researches were achieved on informational materials of the European Education and Culture Executive Agency, Erasmus+ office of the Republic of Moldova, the data of the Ministry of Education of the Republic of Moldova, etc. There were used the following research methods: monographs, comparison, analysis, inference.

Results and discussions

Academic Mobility for staff and students are relevant for State Agrarian University of Moldova (SAUM) because it matches perfectly the main objectives of the institutional Internationalization Strategy (2021-2025) (approved by SAUM Senate on June 30, 2021):

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- internationalization of the curriculum;
- professional and personal development of the staff;
- enhancing university visibility worldwide;
- high quality services offered by SAUM, obtained from learning of the best EU university experience;
- possibility to do joint research activities.

It is important to mention, that due to the opportunity for staff mobility, offered by the Erasmus + program, the following expected activities can be carried out: curriculum' harmonization based on the host country expertise; studying the teaching-learning-assessment technologies applied in the host country; establishing pillars for future cooperation in the following fields: common educational and scientific projects, common researches and publications, participation in scientific events, staff and student mobility, summer schools etc.; improving English language skills of SAUM staff.

Thus, an important aspect of internationalization and namely the internationalization of SAUM curriculum represents a quality requirement and, consequently, it is a criterion for the accreditation. In this context, the academic mobility for staff and students will help to fulfill SAUM strategic objective - to be recognized as an institution that delivers high quality services and to get the accreditation of its study programmes.

Selection process in SAUM is described on the university web page and it is organized according to the following documents:

- Regulations on academic mobility of the State Agrarian University of Moldova, approved by SAUM Senate on the 27th of June, 2014.
- Regulations on the recognition and equivalence of studies that were done within the academic mobility programme, approved by SAUM Administrative Board on July 19, 2016.

SAUM implements mobility within the European Higher Education Area, starting with 2015 (Erasmus + programme). Currently SAUM has signed inter-institutional agreements with 25 HEIs from 14 European Countries.

According to the information from the SAUM Department of International Relations in the period of 2015-2022, 76 staff have realized the academic mobility and 101 students have realized their studies during 1 semester in one of the EU HEI. (fig.1)

Fig.1. Number of STM, STA, STT- outgoing from SAUM

At the same time, academic mobility for staff is welcomed and totally recognized in SAUM:

- as part of the mandatory teachers training abroad;
- as an important component of passing the mandatory contest for vacant positions at university that is organized in accordance with institutional Regulations on the selection criteria for teaching and management positions, conferring scientific and didactic degrees, approved by SAUM Senate on the 4th of April, 2007);
- as part of the teacher’s individual plan for professional development;
- teachers present a report about their academic mobility based on the following documents;
 - documents received from the European university, on the implementation of the academic mobility programme;
 - mandatory presentation at a meeting of the department or Faculty Council regarding the academic mobility carried out abroad;
 - publication of information on the university website regarding the academic mobility in the EU Higher Education Institution.

It is very important to mention that, also, some international students and around 50 EU teachers have visited and they taught lectures at SAUM (fig.2).

Fig. 2. Number of STM, STA, STT- incoming at SAUM

SAUM staff from Department of International Relations offered a lot of services to outgoing students and staff, among them the most important are: information, collaboration, guidance in the visa process and health insurance and English courses.

For incoming staff and students SAUM offer: visa/residence permit support for incoming student/staff, language courses, accommodation on campus, or support in finding accommodation, social and cultural activities for international students, mentor assignments.

In order to disseminate the results of the mobility project at the faculty and institutional levels, the following measures are implemented at SAUM:

- publishing information regarding to ICM projects on the SAUM official website, social media and mass media;
- dissemination of information through Leaflets and brochures, emails;
- announcements about ICM offered by SAUM in the EU HEI placed at Bulletin boards at every Faculty;
- information dissemination regarding ICM though SAUM administrative meetings and deans’ announcements;

- information dissemination through Information Days for SAUM staff and students, held at every Faculty;
- dissemination of information through mass media, social media and participation in various national and international events.

Conclusion and recommendations

We consider the Erasmus + ICM Program to be very appropriate, as both students and teachers improve their language skills, increase the quality of their studies, improve teaching-learning and assessment methods, develop collaborative relationships and conclude interinstitutional agreements. ICM remains one of the indicators performed for the external evaluation of the Cycle 1 and 2 study programs in UASM.

The recommendations of the study include:

1. Increasing the capacity of EU higher education institutions to apply for the projects and to include HEIs from Moldova in their partner list.
2. HEIs from Moldova participation in the credit academic mobility programs by offering university courses in languages of international circulation, developing new curricula, harmonized with the needs of the European labor market, the international promotion of the image of the educational institution, the attraction of students and teachers from other countries.
3. Dissemination of examples of good practice; strengthening the mechanisms of informing students and teachers about the opportunities offered by higher education institutions in the field of academic credit mobility.
4. Diversification by the departments responsible for academic credit mobility of higher education institutions of information pathways target groups, attracting and encouraging students and teachers who have previously participated in academic mobility to provide support to candidates who do not have such experience.
5. Development of institutional policies to increase the degree of access to teachers who encounter difficulties in the mobility process: grants for those with families, keeping the job and the courses taught, offering intensive courses to study modern languages.
6. Ensuring the transparency of teacher selection processes and student who have applied to mobility programs. Publication of analyzes on the processes for submitting applications and the results of the selection of candidates.

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